

Supplementary materials.

Cross-mapping of terms used in chemical risk assessment with those used in systematic review: research protocol

Table S-1. Illustrating the cross-mapping process. [This overview is a detailed version of Table 2.](#)

Step	What
1. Identification of relationships between core CRA terms and core SR terms.	PG will suggest related terms based on the SR definitions derived in phase 3 and the CRA definitions identified in phase 2. PG will finalise the mapping of relationships between the terms after feedback from the SAG.
2. Assembling of an expert group with PG members, SAG members, and additional experts, all self-identifying as having relevant SR and/or CRA expertise.	PG and SAG members will distribute information on the possibility to participate in the expert group through their networks. PG will send information about the role of the expert group members to all interested participants.
3. Discussion of relationships between core terms for study appraisal, evidence integration and evidence synthesis in expert group meetings.	The group will have weekly online meetings and be chaired by a PG member. The expert group will discuss and agree on the relationships between CRA and SR terms. For each meeting, the PG will select 2-5 terms that have been mapped to be related. PG will send terms and their definitions, which will be the starting point for the discussion in the meetings. The information will be sent at least five days before each meeting. The information

Step	What
	<p>will be sent to all persons that have received or been forwarded the meeting invitation.</p> <p>Descriptions of the relationships will be drafted during the discussions.</p>
<p>4. Identification of agreement on discussed descriptions.</p>	<p>After each meeting, the expert group will vote (online) “agree” or “not agree” on the descriptions within five working days. Feedback received after the deadline will not be included.</p> <p>PG will send a reminder on day four to expert group members who have not voted. Votes and feedback received after the deadline will not be included.</p> <p>The criteria for agreement are: i) unanimous voting for “agree” AND ii) ≥ 5 voters.</p> <p>PG will collect votes from the expert group and create an overview of the descriptions where there was agreement and the descriptions where there was no agreement.</p>
<p>5. Suggestion of changes to the descriptions where no agreement was reached.</p>	<p>The expert group will be requested to suggest alternative descriptions for the terms where agreement was not reached. Rationales for the suggested changes should be included.</p> <p>For those descriptions that did reach unanimous agreement, the expert group members will be requested to suggest alternative descriptions together with rationales for the suggested changes.</p> <p>PG will create an overview of all suggested alternative descriptions and the rationales for the suggested changes.</p>

Step	What
6. Discussion of alternative descriptions in expert group meetings	The alternative descriptions will be discussed in a second meeting. The alternative definitions will be distributed to the expert group members by a PG member five working days before the meeting. The definitions are revised according to the discussion.
7. Identification of agreement on discussed alternative descriptions.	Same process as step 5. The criteria for agreement for definitions for terms that are discussed for the second time are: i) at least 80% of the voters voted “agree” AND ii) ≥5 voters.
8. Repeat steps 6 to 8 for descriptions where no agreement was reached.	For those descriptions where agreement was not reached after three rounds of voting, no statement of the relationship between the CRA and the SR terms will be created. However, information on the difficulties and suggested descriptions will be included as supplementary materials.
9. Publishing of the descriptions of the relationship between the SR and the CRA terms.	PG will draft the manuscript and all co-authors review the manuscript before submission by the PG.

Table S-2. Illustrating the presentation of the SR and CRA core terms. For each term, the five experts rated (5-point Likert scale; where 5 indicates strong agreement and 1 indicates strong disagreement) whether they agree that the term is a core term within SR or CRA for study appraisal, evidence synthesis or evidence integration.

Term	Score (times rated 4 or 5)	Score (cumulative sum of ratings)	SR Term (yes or no)	CRA term (yes or no)
Term 1	1	12	Yes	No

Term 2	3	17	No	Yes
Term 3	2	13	Yes	Yes
Term 4	5	22	No	Yes

Table S-3. Illustrating the presentation of the catalogued definitions of the core CRA terms.

Core CRA term (in alphabetical order)	CRA Term Definition
Term 1	[Definition 1]
	[Definition 2]
	[Definition 3]
	[Definition 4]
Term 2	[Definition 1]
	[Definition 2]
	[Definition 3]
Term 3	[Definition 1]
	[Definition 2]
Etc.	

Table S-4. Illustrating the presentation of the catalogued definitions of the core SR terms.

Core SR term (in alphabetical order)	SR Term Definition
Term 1	[Definition 1]
	[Definition 2]
	[Definition 3]
	[Definition 4]
Term 2	[Definition 1]
	[Definition 2]
	[Definition 3]
Term 3	[Definition 1]
	[Definition 2]
Etc.	

Table S-5. Illustrating the final presentation of the cross-mapping of CRA terms on the SR terms. The SR terms “external validity”, “internal validity”, “precision”, and “validity”, and the CRA terms “generalisability”, “relevance”, and “reliability” are used as examples.

CRA Term	CRA Term Definitions	Related SR Terms	SR Term Definition	Cross-mapping – description of relationships between terms
Reliability	[definition 1] [definition 2] [definition 3]	Internal validity	[definition 1] [definition 2]	Tendency toward truth is internal validity in SR, whereas consistency of results is more of a precision-related concept (an imprecise study will tend toward the truth on multiple repetitions, but in a one-off situation it will not be clear how close to the truth the measurement is, hence not being reliable).

Table S-6. Illustrating the SR terms and the related CRA terms and conceptual overlap.

SR Term	SR Term Definition	Related CRA Terms	Related CRA Term Definitions
Internal validity	[definition 1] [definition 2]	Reliability	[definition 1] [definition 2] [definition 3]
		Validity	[definition 1] [definition 2]
External validity	[definition 1] [definition 2] [definition 3]	Generalisability	[definition 1]
		Relevance	[definition 1] [definition 2]
		Validity	[definition 1] [definition 2]
Indirectness	Synonym of external validity	See External Validity	

Table S-7. Participant characteristics of experts participating in online meetings in phase 3 for the identification of conceptual overlap between CRA and SR terms. The table summarises characteristics of the participants that participated in two or more meetings. “N” indicates the number of participants selecting an alternative.

Country of residence	Country A Country B Country C and so on. <i>In alphabetical order</i>
Main employer	Main employer A Main employer B Main employer C and so on. <i>In alphabetical order</i>
Type of profession	Profession A: N Profession B: N Profession C: N and so on. <i>In alphabetical order</i>
Do you describe yourself as a man, a woman, or in some other way?	Man Woman Other
Age	≤24 years: N 25-34 years: N 35-44 years: N 45-54 years: N 55-64 years: N ≥65 years
Experience with chemical risk assessment	No experience: N Some experience (<i>e.g., been involved in one chemical risk assessment</i>): N Moderate experience (<i>conducted study appraisal or hazard identification in at least one chemical risk assessment or participated in several chemical risk assessments</i>): N

	Extensive experience (<i>was the main risk assessor for at least one chemical risk or participated in more than five chemical risk assessments</i>): N
Experience with systematic reviews	No experience: N Some experience (<i>e.g., been involved in one systematic review or peer-reviewed several systematic reviews</i>): N Moderate experience (<i>conducted study appraisal in at least one systematic review</i>): N Extensive experience (<i>have designed the methods, including selection, modification, or developed study assessment methods, for at least one systematic review</i>): N

S-8. Invitation text for recruitment of additional experts.

Project Title

Cross-mapping between of terms used in chemical risk assessment with those used in systematic review: research protocol

Project Description

The focus on implementation of systematic review (SR) principles in chemical risk assessments (CRAs) is growing as it has the potential to advance the rigour and transparency of the CRAs. However, the SR and CRA communities use their own specific terminologies. Understanding the meaning of core SR and CRA terms and where they overlap is critical for application of SR methods and principles in CRAs.

A cross-mapping of core SR and CRA terms will be performed to explore the relationship between the terms and to identify conceptual overlaps. Weekly online meetings with self-identifying experts will be conducted.

The protocol for the project can be viewed [here](#).

Who can participate?

We are interested in people having experience in systematic reviews, chemical risk assessments or both. There are no specific criteria for participation and extensive experience is not a requirement.

How to contribute

There are two ways of contributing to the Project. Each is of equal value.

1. By participating in *discussion* of terms and definitions on live calls. These are hosted on Teams and held weekly, currently at Xpm EST time on [Weekday]. The live calls are for drafting the descriptions of the relationships between the discussed terms and definitions.
2. By *voting and commenting* on the description of the relationships between the discussed terms and definitions.

How to sign up

We will arrange weekly online meetings (duration 1 hour) to discuss relationships between CRA and SR terms.

To participate, send an e-mail to gro.haarklou.mathisen@vkm.no to be added to the expert list. You will then receive the invitations for the online meetings. A minimum of five days before each meeting, the terms and definitions will be sent out for all persons signed up to the expert list.

There are no obligations connected to signing up to the expert list. It is not necessary to inform us if you can attend a meeting or not – you can just show up for the meetings that fit your schedule.

Co-authorship

Expert Group members are eligible to be co-authors if they i) vote and/or comment on at least ten terms or cross-mappings in total, and ii) reviews the manuscript. Expert group members not eligible to be co-authors will be listed in the acknowledgements. No financial compensation or other incentives are offered for the participation as additional expert.